

Determinants of Quality of Life of Public Prosecutors in Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 03, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 04, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Occupational Stress, Quality Of Life, Job Satisfaction, Emotional Intelligence, Public Prosecutors</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7145403</p>	<p><i>The job of public prosecutors is quite demanding. They face multiple challenges at their workplace. When they are not able to address these challenges successfully, they feel stress that not only negatively affects their job satisfaction, but also lowers their quality of life. The current study was carried out to examine the role of occupational stress, job satisfaction, and emotional intelligence in the quality of life of public prosecutors in Pakistan. A sample of 350 public prosecutors (Men = 306, Women = 44) from Punjab, Pakistan was taken. Demographic datasheet, Scale of Emotional Intelligence, Occupational Stress Scale for Public Prosecutors, Job satisfaction survey, World Health Organization Quality of Life scale (WHOQOL-BREF) were used as data collection tools. Results of Pearson correlation analysis indicated that quality of life had significant negative relationships with occupational stress ($r = -.33, p < .01$) and job satisfaction ($r = -.27, p < .01$), and positive, but non-significant relationship with emotional intelligence. Hierarchical regression analysis indicated that 13.7 percent variance in quality of life was accounted for by occupational stress and job satisfaction, after controlling demographic variables.</i></p>

Introduction

Quality of Life (QOL) appeared as a subject of attention, when psychologists started talking about workers' stressful working conditions (Katsching & Krautgartner, 2002). According to World Health Organization, QOL is physical, mental, and social well-being of an individual (WHO, 1995). It is defined as "an individual's perception of his/her position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which he/she lives and in relation to his/her goals, expectations, standards and concerns" (Rusli et al., 2008).

QOL can be divided into three groups: subjective, objective, and existential quality of life. Subjective quality of life refers to the feeling of an individual of how good a life one perceives. Objective quality of life is how a person's life is perceived by the outside world. Existential quality of life is how best one's life is at a deeper level. Deep down somewhere a person has a desire to be respected and loved. The fulfillment of these deeper desires indicates a good existential quality of life (Ventegodt et al., 2003).

Successful organizations are currently promoting wellbeing and ensuring the quality of life for their employees through improving social connections, prevention of theft, violence, and economic exploitation, making sure that all employees get property rights and providing the individuals, reasonable opportunities to get involved in the political process. Through engaging social contracts and developing civic engagement in an organization, employee happiness can be stimulated that eventually leads to the formation of economic development of the organization. On the other hand, institutes that have a reputation for inefficiency and corruption tend to produce high levels of psychological dysfunction among employees that negatively impact their quality of life (Nikolova, 2016).

Improving the quality of life of employees is an organization's priority, if they want the institute to work in the same direction and create a balance between work life and family life. Organizations mostly aspire to develop an environment, where individuals can be more cooperative towards each other and introduce positive changes to the workplace in helping them achieve their goals (Bhatnagar & Soni, 2015).

It is evident from the literature that quality of life is an amalgamation of various factors. The data concerning public prosecutors is scarce however, Bibas (2011) highlights that overwork harms justice and adversely affects the quality of life of the prosecutors.

One of the main determinants of workers' health is occupational stress, which is detrimental to the extent that it results into burnout and disturbs quality of life – becoming a global concern (Sinval et al., 2019), eventually leading to decrease in job satisfaction or change of profession (Pinto et al., 2003). Studies have shown that shortage of court staff, and poor physical and material conditions of judicial workplaces are obstacles in decreasing judicial professionals' work performance as well as their quality of life (Ferreira, 2011; Guimarães et al., 2017).

Workplace stress also has a negative impact on mental health of employees, whereas judicial personnel with stable physical and mental health shall be able to make decisions without compromising the provision of quality of justice to citizens (Na et al., 2018).

Emotional intelligence helps to manage stress successfully. Individuals with higher emotional intelligence (EI) are more mindful of their feelings and are more successful to manage pressure-related feelings, all of which lead to more elevated levels of prosperity / well-being. Empirical studies have demonstrated that EI positively correlates with QOL, and a negative relationship was found between job stress and QOL (Min, 2014). Anjum and Swathi (2017). Also reported a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and quality of life.

Occupational stress gives rise to unwanted and unfavorable impacts on employees in terms of low organizational commitment and low job satisfaction (Leather et al., 2003) and Job satisfaction is a significant social determinant of wellbeing. A study assessed the relationship between job satisfaction and quality of life in staff members of the Ilam University of clinical sciences. The outcomes exhibited a positive relationship between job satisfaction and QOL. Likewise, the most significant factors influencing the job satisfaction of workers were job experience, marital status, job status, and essentialness. Results showed positive relationship between quality of life related with wellbeing and job satisfaction of the laborers (Hosainabadi et al., 2018).

It is shocking to see that prosecutors and their work-related problems have received very less attention from social scientists (Jocoby, 1980; McDonald, 1979). Job of judges and public prosecutors is psychologically demanding and extremely challenging. Studies show that prosecutors face severe forms of occupational stress due to the physically and emotionally demanding nature of their work. Their job is to uphold justice and they are entrusted to extract truth from the legally conflicting information provided to them each day. These tasks preside intense pressure and lead towards stress that has adverse effects on the health of prosecutors. Social scientists are now interested to carry out empirical studies on the components and correlates of stress among public prosecutors

Considering arduous nature of the work environment and the several responsibilities public prosecutors have to carry out (Bishop & Osler, 2015; Green & Roiphe, 2017), there arises the need to assess the workplace stress and stressors of public prosecutors working in various countries. Stressful work conditions, and decision makings of prosecutors affect multiple arenas directly or indirectly: from the well-being of prosecutors to the lives of the accused, the victims, their families, or even the public. Those prosecutors, who are affected negatively and consequently, get dissatisfied and would barely give their best at workplace (Na et al., 2018).

Provided that job of public prosecutors is quite demanding and stressful and in the long run, stress brings multiple health hazards and physical and psychological illnesses, and is harmful for the employees' health and the output of the organization, it seems imperative to measure their stress and its occupational and health related consequences empirically. Quality of life of employees determines the success of any organization. So, the present study was designed to test personal and work-related determinants (viz., emotional intelligence, stress, and job satisfaction) of quality of life of public prosecutors.

Hypotheses

1. There are significant relationships among emotional intelligence, occupational stress, job satisfaction, and quality of life of public prosecutors.
2. Emotional intelligence, occupational stress, and job satisfaction significantly predict quality of life of public prosecutors by controlling demographic variables.

Method

Sample

A purposive sampling technique was used to obtain a sample of 350 public prosecutors from 10 cities of Punjab (Lahore, Sheikhpura, Kasur, Faisalabad, Chiniot, Bahawalpur, Multan, Jehlum, Gujranwala, and Sialkot). Sample comprised of ADPPs and DDPPs (assistant district public prosecutor and deputy district public prosecutor). The sample consisted of 306 male and 44 female public prosecutors, with at least 3 years of experience in the public prosecution department.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The sample included those public prosecutors who were working in the field (dealing in courts) and not in the administration department.

Instruments

Demographic Data Sheet

Demographic data sheet contains all the information relevant to various personal/demographic factors (viz., gender, age, work experience, marital status and family system)

Scale of Emotional Intelligence (SEI)

Scale of Emotional Intelligence (SEI) is a 56-items scale developed by Batool and Khalid (2011). SEI is a 4-point Likert-type scale (1=*never*, 2=*seldom*, 3=*sometimes*, 4=*often*, 5=*always*) to record the responses of the participants and has 10 subscales; interpersonal skill, self-regard, assertiveness, emotional self-awareness,

empathy, impulse control, flexibility, problem solving, stress tolerance, and optimism. The overall reliability of the scale is reported to be .64

Occupational Stress Scale for Public Prosecutors

Occupational Stress Scale for Public Prosecutors (OSSPP) is a 26-item scale developed in part I of the project. It measures the occupational stress in public prosecutors on 5-point Likert type scale (1=*strongly disagree*, 2=*disagree*, 3=*neutral*, 4=*agree*, 5 *strongly agree*). It has 5 subscales; lack of facilities, interdepartmental challenges, motivational issues, personal life and health, and administrative issues (Bilal & Batool, 2021). The overall reliability of the scale is reported to be .89.

Job Satisfaction Survey

Job satisfaction survey (JSS) is a 36-item scale developed by Spector in 1985. The scale comprises 9 subscales and uses 6-point Likert-type scale (1=*disagree very much*, 2=*disagree moderately*, 3=*disagree slightly*, 4=*agree slightly*, 5=*agree moderately*, 6=*agree very much*) to record the responses of the participants. The overall reliability of the scale is reported to be $\alpha = .80$.

World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF)

World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF) is a 26-item scale; out of which 24 items measure four different domains; physical health, psychological, social relationships, and environment, whereas rest of the 2 items measure general quality of life. WHOQOL-BREF is a 5-point Likert type scale (1=*very poor*, 2=*poor*, 3=*neither poor nor good*, 4=*good*, 5=*very good*) to assess individual's quality of life. Every item represents different component of life. Higher scores on each item signify better quality of life. The results should be interpreted by domain since there is no overall score (WHOQoL Group, 1997). The overall reliability of the scale is reported to be $\alpha = .84$

Procedure

After the approval of topic from Advanced Studies and Research Board (AS&RB) of GC University, permission was sought from the director of center for professional development of public prosecutors (CPD). Set of questionnaires including 26 items OSSPP, 36 items JSS, 56 items SEI and 26 items WHOQOL-BREF were administered to 380 participants of public prosecution department of Punjab. Only 350 participants responded out of 380. Data were collected from Public Prosecutors by personally visiting them in their offices after office timings. They were given special instructions to complete the questionnaires honestly and carefully. Upon meet-up, their consent was taken, the aim of the study was briefed, and they were promised that their identities would always remain confidential. They were also told that any participant could back out from the research any time. Participants were given informed consent to sign and then were provided with all the Likert type response format questionnaires. Participants took 25-40 minutes to complete all the questionnaires. The researcher eventually ran statistical analyses on a sample of 350 participants via SPSS 20.0 version and AMOS.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables (N=350)

Variable	M	SD	α	Range	
				Potential	Actual
1. SEI	104.43	10.75	.64	56-224	80-138
2. JSS	122.47	18.63	.80	36-216	93-171
3. QOL	68.52	16.40	.84	26-130	29-105
4. OSSPP	96.42	11.18	.89	26-130	71-122

Note. SEI: Scale of Emotional Intelligence, JSS: Job Satisfaction Survey, QOL: Quality of Life, OSSPP: Occupational Stress Scale for Public Prosecutors

Table 1 represents the Cronbach alpha values of the scales used in the study ranges from .64 to .89. Furthermore, the table shows potential and actual ranges of the scales (scale of emotional intelligence, job satisfaction survey, quality of life and occupational stress scale for public prosecutors) used in the current study. Mean value on OSSPP shows that public prosecutors scored higher on stress. Whereas, mean values on SEI, JSS and QOL show moderate level of scores on these variables.

Table 2

Correlations among Study Variables (N=350)

Variable	1	2	3
1. SEI	-		
2. JSS	.12*	-	
3. QOL	.02	.27**	-
4. OSSPP	-.12*	-.30**	-.33**

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Note. SEI: Scale of Emotional Intelligence, JSS: Job Satisfaction Survey, QOL: Quality of Life, OSSPP: Occupational Stress Scale for Public Prosecutors

Emotional intelligence has a significant positive relationship with job satisfaction, significant negative relationship with occupational stress, and a non-significant relationship with quality of life. Higher the emotional intelligence, higher would-be job satisfaction and lower would-be occupational stress. Job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with emotional intelligence and quality of life, whereas it has significant negative relationship with occupational stress. Occupational stress has significant negative relationships with emotional intelligence, quality of life and job satisfaction. Higher the occupational stress, lower would-be job satisfaction and quality of life.

Table 3

Hierarchical Regression Analysis for predicting Quality of Life from Occupational Stress, Emotional Intelligence, and Job Satisfaction, While Controlling Demographic Variables (N=350)

	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β	R ²	ΔR ²
		LL	UL				
Step 1							
Constant	74.06	61.44	86.68	6.41		.02	.02
Age	0.50	-2.85	3.84	1.70	.02		
Gender	0.82	-4.43	6.07	2.67	.02		
Years of Service	1.1	-0.92	4.73	1.44	.07		
Marital Status	-4.97	-9.19	-0.76	2.14	-.14		
Family Orientation	-1.66	-7.01	3.68	2.72	-.03		
Step 2							
Constant	117.57	99.29	135.84	9.29		.11	.09
Age	1.19	-1.99	4.37	1.62	.04		
Gender	-2.31	-7.39	2.77	2.58	-.05		
Years of Service	1.36	-1.32	4.05	1.37	.05		
Marital Status	-1.95	-6.06	2.16	2.09	-.06		
Family system	0.19	-4.91	5.30	2.59	.01		
OSSPP	-0.49	-0.65	-0.34	0.08	-.34***		
Step 3							
Constant	121.22	96.41	146.03	12.61		.11	.00
Age	1.22	-1.97	4.42	1.62	.04		
Gender	-2.28	-7.37	2.81	2.58	-.04		
Years of Service	1.388	-1.31	4.07	1.37	.05		
Marital Status	-1.89	-6.02	2.23	2.09	-.05		
Family system	0.37	-4.81	5.55	2.63	.01		
OSSPP	-0.50	-0.66	-0.34	0.08	-.34***		
SEI	-0.34	-0.19	0.12	0.07	-.02		
Step 4							
Constant	92.01	63.66	120.36	14.41		.15	.04
Age	1.60	-1.52	4.72	1.59	.06		
Gender	-2.03	-7.01	2.96	2.54	-.04		
Years of Service	1.69	-0.94	4.34	1.34	.06		
Marital Status	-1.89	-5.93	2.15	2.05	-.05		
Family system	1.24	-3.85	6.33	2.58	.02		
OSSPP	-0.42	-0.58	0.25	0.08	-.28***		
SEI	-0.07	-0.22	0.08	0.07	-.04		
JSS	0.18	0.09	0.27	0.05	.21***		

*** $p < .001$

Hierarchical regression is performed to assess the variance in quality of life, predicted by occupational stress, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction while controlling demographic variables; age, gender, years of service, marital status and family system. Multicollinearity assumption is tested and all variables have inter-correlations less than .4, and tolerance values greater than .10 and VIF less than 10. Hence the assumption is fulfilled.

Overall model is significant and explain 15% variance in quality of life ($F(7,342) = 9.12, p < .001$) accounted for by occupational stress and job satisfaction while age, gender, years of service, marital status and family system are controlled. Occupational stress ($\beta = -.28***$) was a significant negative predictor and job satisfaction ($\beta = .21***$) was a significant positive predictor of quality of life, while emotional intelligence ($\beta = -.04$) does not appear as a significant predictor of quality of life. Results also show that when in step 4 JSS is

entered in the model, the β value of OSSPP decreases from -.34 to -.28, which indicates that JSS mediates between the relationship of OSSPP and QOL.

Discussion

The current study was carried out to assess the correlates of quality of life (i.e., emotional intelligence, occupational stress, and job satisfaction) among public prosecutors in Pakistan. We primarily assessed inter-correlations among study variables as a prerequisite of regression analysis, to ascertain the degree and direction of relationship between study variables. Results of Pearson's correlation analysis indicated that occupational stress and job satisfaction had inverse relationship and had significant negative and positive correlations with quality of life of public prosecutors, respectively (see Table 2). Occupational stress and job satisfaction also appeared as significant predictors of QOL of public prosecutors (see Table 3). Results are in line with previous literature that concludes that there exists a positive relationship between job satisfaction and quality of life (Yu et al., 2008) and a negative relationship between occupational stress and quality of life (Jafari et al., 2012). Results are also in line with Johnson et al.' (2005) study that lower occupational stress predicts higher job satisfaction. Occupational stress gives rise to unwanted and unfavorable impacts on employees in terms of low organizational commitment and decreased job satisfaction (Leather et al., 2003). Job satisfaction reduces as stress increases (Antoniou et al., 2003), and job satisfaction brings forth improved performance of employees. If occupational stress prolongs, it tends to be a prime contributor to health problems and a number of problems for organizations in terms of absenteeism, dissatisfaction, low productivity, and turnover (Garg & Rastogi, 2009; Hochberg et al., 2013; Marchland et al., 2009).

Results are also consistent with the empirical studies that indicate that higher activity stress is related to lower quality of life, which is an inexorably regular pointer to survey a person's overall wellbeing status, psychological wellbeing, and prosperity (Min, 2014). Results are consistent with the empirical literature that employees' satisfaction with their job, improves their quality of life (Cimete et al., 2003; Hosainabadi et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2008). Results are in line with the previous studies that indicated job stress as a risk factor for the quality of life of employees (Li et al., 2019; Mei-Chin et al., 2014; Ribeiro et al., 2018).

Employees who have high work-related stress, they complain about health problems and job dissatisfaction (Rusli et al., 2008). If we look at the documented reasons of health problems and job dissatisfaction of employees, there are numerous like; workplace demands such as to remain in professional competition, and to keep striving to fulfill job duties for greater productivity while ignoring stressors, which is harmful for employees' mental and physical health (Jahanzeb, 2010).

Non-significant relationship of emotional intelligence with QoL of public prosecutors is contrary to the existing literature, which seems awkward. Our result is supported by Aghdasi et al. (2011). While qualifying the non-significant role of EI in job outcomes among the employees of developing countries, Aghdasi et al. (2011) proclaims that ability of EI would only be beneficial if lower-level needs are fulfilled. While explaining his approach, Aghdasi et al. (2011) uses Mayer et al.'s (2004) definition of emotional intelligence and the theory of hierarchy of needs by Maslow (1954), relating to the concept of self-actualization and job satisfaction. According to Maslow (1954), lowest level needs include physiological and safety needs, whereas self-actualization is the highest-level need, while a person with the high ability of EI reaches to the stage of self-actualization (Aghdasi et al., 2011). As Maslow (1954) says that higher level needs arise as soon as the lower-level needs get fulfilled, hence, keeping job environment into consideration, if needs related to payment, job security, respect toward all the stakeholders of the organization are not satisfied, then need of self-actualization and attention to oneself would not even arise. When economic growth and facilitation are not sufficient, lower-level needs of employees would remain unsatisfied. Subsequently, higher level needs would not arise and needs of individuals would be left at lower level. Therefore, employees would never be satisfied with higher level of needs (Robbins, 2005). Experts, nowadays, consider EI as the tool to reduce occupational stress and increase job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Nonetheless, the ability of EI would only be beneficial if lower-level needs are fulfilled. In public prosecution department in developing countries like Pakistan, employees' basic needs are not fulfilled due to organizational and administration's fundamental problems such as unfavorable working conditions, lack of facilities, non-supportive structures, relatively unattractive compensation models, and related. Whereas, the picture of working environment is quite different in developed countries such as USA, Canada, China, England, and Australia, where lower-level needs are satisfied and consequently employees start paying heed to fulfill their higher-level need (Aghdasi et al., 2011).

Implications

The present study has made significant contribution in the existing pool of literature. Job stress of public prosecutors appeared to have delirious impact on both job consequences (job satisfaction) and health outcomes (quality of life), so organizational psychologists should be hired, or the services of counselor need to be requested to address the stress of public prosecutors.

Limitations and suggestions

The researcher focused profoundly on the literature in the fields of occupational stress, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, and quality of life in general because sufficient theoretical or empirical work on public prosecutors' work stressors and their outcomes is not available, there is a dire need to focus on more specific contextual and situational factors particularly related to public prosecutors.

The need also arises to work on customized stress management techniques for public prosecutors to practice to overcome their work-related stressors, but due to time constraint, we leave it for future researchers to develop stress management plan that can be used to help them overcome day-to-day stressors of public prosecutors, so that their quality of life can be improved.

Conclusion

Results of the current study imply that public prosecutors in Pakistan experience manifold stressors in different domains of their job that lowers their job satisfaction and has detrimental impact on their quality of life. Occupational stress not only has direct detrimental impact on quality of life of public prosecutors, but also indirectly affects their QoL via job satisfaction. It means that negative job outcomes of occupational stress spillover to their well-being and QoL.

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